

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING AS A MEANS OF INTENSIFYING THE STUDY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AT A UNIVERSITY

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Annotation: This article provides a definition of critical thinking, the study of the goals and structure of technology, basic techniques, and a lesson model within the framework of this technology. Presentation of your experience, the use of this technology in literature and Russian language lessons, its effectiveness at different stages of lessons, in different types of lessons. Selection of didactic material for classes using this technology. Development of individual lesson elements, lesson models in accordance with the structure of this technology.

Key words: Russian language, literature, model, didactic material, lessons, students, critical thinking.

Critical thinking (CT) is one of the types of human intellectual activity, which is characterized by a high level of perception, understanding, objectivity of approach to the surrounding information field, it is a search for common sense, the ability to act logically, taking into account one's point of view, as well as other opinions and give up your own prejudices. A person who thinks critically is able to come up with new ideas and see new possibilities. Critical thinking leads a person to self-improvement.

Critical thinking, as stated by Professor David Clouster, a volunteer for the Reading and Writing Critical Thinking Program:

- this is independent thinking;
- information is the starting point, and not the final point of critical thinking;
- Critical thinking begins with asking questions and understanding the problems that need to be solved;
- Critical thinking strives for convincing argumentation;
- Critical thinking is social thinking.

Many famous didactic scientists (J. Dewey, B. Bloom and others) believe that it is necessary to give the student the opportunity to set learning goals that create the necessary internal motive for the learning process. Only then can the teacher choose effective methods to achieve these goals. It is best to assimilate information on a topic about which we already know something. It's easier to make a decision when what we do is consistent with our experience[1].

The first task of the challenge stage is to provide the student with the opportunity to analyze what he already knows about the topic being studied; this will create an additional incentive for him to formulate his own goals and motives.

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The second task is to intensify the cognitive activity of students. It is important that during the challenge phase everyone can take part in the work aimed at updating their own experience. It is also important to systematize all the information that appears as a result of students' own statements. This way, they will be able to see the collected information as whole, with contradictions and unclear points, which will initiate a search as they learn new information.

Students can express their point of view on the topic being studied, and do so freely, without fear of making mistakes, that is, to be freely communicated and corrected by the teacher. It is important to record statements; any of them will be important for further work. At this stage there are no "right" or "wrong" statements. A combination of individual and group work is important. Individual work allows each student to update their knowledge and experience. Group work allows you to hear the opinions of others and express your point of view without the risk of making mistakes. Working in small groups allows students to feel more comfortable. The role of the teacher is to stimulate students to conversation, conflict-free exchange of opinions in groups, recording and systematizing information. It is important not to criticize the answers, to follow the rule: "Any student's opinion is valuable." If the challenge phase is successfully implemented, students have a powerful incentive to work at the next stage - the stage of obtaining new information[2].

This stage is also called the semantic stage. Typically, learning new material takes the longest time. The fast pace of presentation of new material in the mode of listening and writing practically eliminates the possibility of comprehending it. One of the conditions for the development of critical thinking is to monitor your understanding when working with the material being studied. Students in the challenge phase have determined the directions of their knowledge, so the teacher, in the process of explanation, has the opportunity to place emphasis in accordance with the expectations and questions asked. The organization of work at this stage may be different. This could be a story, a lecture, individual, pair or group reading, or watching videos. In any case, it will be individual acceptance and tracking of information.

The authors of pedagogical technology for the development of critical thinking note that in the process of implementing the semantic stage, the main task is to maintain the activity of students, their interest and the inertia of movement created during the challenge phase. In this sense, the quality of the selected material is important. At the semantic stage, students independently continue to actively

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construct the goals of their learning. Setting goals in the process of learning new information is carried out when it is superimposed on existing knowledge. Students can find answers to previously posed questions and solve difficulties that arose at the initial stage of work. But not all questions and difficulties can be resolved. In this case, it is important that the teacher encourages students to pose new questions and search for answers through the context of the information with which students are working[2].

“Reflection is a special type of thinking. Reflective thinking means focusing your attention. It means careful weighing, evaluation and choice,” notes Robert Boostrom in *Developing Creative and Critical Thinking*. In the process of reflection, the information that was new becomes appropriated and turns into one’s own knowledge. Reflexive analysis and evaluation permeate the previous stages of work. But reflection in the challenge and implementation phases has other forms and functions. At the third stage, reflection of the process becomes the main goal of the activities of schoolchildren and teachers.

Reflective analysis is aimed at clarifying the meaning of new material, building a further learning route (what is clear, what is not, what else needs to be learned about, questions asked, and so on). But analysis is of little use if it is not expressed in verbal or written form. It is in the process of voicing that the chaos of thoughts that was in the mind during independent comprehension is systematized and transformed into new knowledge.

Questions and doubts that arise can be resolved. In the process of exchanging opinions about what they read or heard, students have the opportunity to realize that the same text can cause different evaluations that differ in form and content. Some of the judgments of other students may be quite acceptable to accept as your own. Other judgments call for discussion. The lively exchange of ideas between students provides an opportunity to expand their expressive vocabulary as well as to be exposed to different concepts. By allowing dialogue at the reflection stage, the teacher makes it possible to see and consider different opinions on the same issue.

The combination of individual and group work at this stage is most appropriate. In the process of individual work (various types of writing: essays, keywords, graphic organization, etc.), students select the information that is most significant for understanding the essence of the topic being studied and the most significant for the implementation of previously set individual goals. Students also express new ideas and information in their own words and independently build cause-and-effect

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relationships. Students remember best what they understand in their own context by expressing it in their own words. Such understanding is durable and creates a personal, meaningful context[3].

Reflection helps to track not only the results of learning, but also the learning process itself, the process of thinking and activity. K. Rogers expressed the essence of reflective learning as follows: “The way to learn is to identify your doubts, try to clarify unclear issues and thus get closer to the meaning of new experience.” How can a teacher stimulate reflection? Questions can be an effective mechanism. Teacher questions are a way to stimulate the activity of the reflection process and a way to show students the path to independent reflection. Encouraging students to ask questions is the most important and most difficult task of a teacher in the learning process, which requires systematic work.

If you look at the three stages of classes described above from the point of view of a traditional lesson, it becomes obvious that they are familiar to the teacher and are not something exclusively new. They are almost always present, just called differently. The challenge stage is an introduction to the problem, updating the students’ existing experience and knowledge. Comprehension is learning new material. Reflection in a traditional lesson is a reinforcement of the material and a check of learning. New, in addition to philosophical ideas, which the use of technology for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing in the lessons of Russian language and literature provides, is contained in methodological techniques that are focused on creating conditions for the free development of each individual.

What results do we achieve by applying the technology of developing critical thinking through reading and writing in Russian language and literature lessons? By using technology, we create favorable conditions for improving the quality of education in the subject, for the subsequent self-realization of students, their successful self-development; We activate students’ activities and increase their learning motivation. We move away from simple retelling of events, give students the opportunity to work with the information themselves, assimilate it, repeat and listen to it several times, involve all children in active work, teach them to highlight the main thing in the text, and formulate their conclusions. And in the conditions of the modern flow of information, this is one of the most important competencies that a language arts teacher must develop.

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